

Cauchy Schwarz Inequality-Fourier Transform-Lagrange Multiplier Equivalence

코시 슈바르츠 부등식-푸리에 변환-라그랑주 승수법 동등성

윤지현(Jihyeon Yoon)
somehowme@gmail.com, flyingtext@nate.com
(Amateur Mathematician, Shinhwa Geriatric Hospital)

2024. 7. 15

Abstract

[한글] 코시 슈바르츠 부등식과 푸리에 변환, 라그랑주 승수법은 2가지 측면에서 동등성을 가진다. 첫째로 고정점을 기반으로 한다는 동등성이다. 둘째로 기존에 주어진 속성에 대하여 기저를 변환의 대상으로 삼아 초평면을 만든다는 동등성이다.

[English] Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, Fourier Transformation, and Lagrange multiplier have equivalence in two aspects. First, they are based on fixed points. Second, they target transformation based on primarily given properties to hyperplane.

1 Introduction

Note that all the notations and preconditions in this paper follows the example of the citation[김성기(2011)]. In this paper, equivalences of Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, Lagrange multiplier, and Fourier Transformation will be discussed. Where will be as follows:

1. Transformation from fixed points as eigenvalue
2. Transformation to adventing new relations

2 Transformation: Basis, Function and Function Sequence

2.1 Fixed Points: Inversible in Eigenvalue

Basically, Cauchy-Schwarz inequality is about vector, Lagrange multiplier is about function, Fourier Transformation is about function sequence especially in relatable timely manner.

2.1.1 Cauchy-Schwarz Inequality

Fixed points in Cauchy-Schwarz inequality can be regarded as eigenvalue of given vectors.

$$|\langle u, v \rangle|^2 \leq \langle u, u \rangle \cdot \langle v, v \rangle$$

With setting basis set in $u, u', u'', \dots \in \mathbb{R}^n$:

$$\text{Basis } \mathcal{B} = \{u, u', u'', \dots\} \text{ s.t. } u \perp u' \perp u'' \perp \dots$$

As it is well known that:

$$|\langle \vec{0}, \vec{0} \rangle|^2 \leq \langle \vec{0}, \vec{0} \rangle \cdot \langle \vec{0}, \vec{0} \rangle$$

Assuming that $f(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) = |\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle|$, $g(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) = \langle \vec{x}, \vec{x} \rangle \cdot \langle \vec{y}, \vec{y} \rangle$ and $f(\vec{0}, \vec{0}) = 0$, $g(\vec{0}, \vec{0}) = 0$ as fixed point in \mathbb{R}^n :

$$\begin{aligned}
f(f(f(\dots(n)\dots f(\vec{a}_1, \vec{a}_2), \vec{a}_3), \vec{a}_4)\dots)) &\leq f(f(f(\dots(n-1)\dots f(g(\vec{a}_1, \vec{a}_2), \vec{a}_3), \vec{a}_4)\dots)) \\
&\leq f(f(f(\dots(n-1)\dots g(f(\vec{a}_1, \vec{a}_2), \vec{a}_3), \vec{a}_4)\dots)) \\
&\leq f(f(f(\dots(n-1)\dots g(g(\vec{a}_1, \vec{a}_2), \vec{a}_3), \vec{a}_4)\dots))
\end{aligned}$$

Ordered Lagrange multipliers appear with every function composited as fixed.

2.1.2 Fourier Transformation

$$F(x) = a_1 \sin \theta_1 + a_2 \sin \theta_2 + a_3 \sin \theta_3 + \dots$$

This equals sum of sequence $\langle a, \theta \rangle$. With applying to upper Cauchy-Schwarz inequality occasion, assuming $\langle a \rangle, \langle \sin \theta \rangle$:

$$|\langle a, \sin \theta \rangle|^2 \leq \langle a, a \rangle \cdot \langle \sin \theta, \sin \theta \rangle$$

This simple relation continues to discussion in hyperplane.

2.1.3 Lagrange Multiplier

Fixed points in Lagrange multiplier can be regarded as additional dimension in famous case of SVM(Support Vector Machine). Current discussions so to here are applications of Lagrange multiplier in different forms.

2.2 New Relations: Hyperplane

All three cases directs the advent of hyperplane. In all these three cases assume transformation to be equal to relation by transformation. This property is equivalent to usage of hyperplane.

2.2.1 Cauchy-Schwarz Inequality

Hyperplane in Cauchy-Schwarz inequality can be regarded as unique value as trace in vectors.

$$|\langle u, v \rangle|^2 \leq \langle u, u \rangle \cdot \langle v, v \rangle$$

For $u, u' \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ and $u' := u_{n+1} \cdot (\dots, 0)$:

$$|\langle u, u' \rangle|^2 \leq \langle u, u \rangle \cdot \langle u', u' \rangle$$

This Cauchy-Schwarz inequality adds basis by comparing with u' . This basis can be regarded as hyperplane. With trace:

$$\begin{aligned}
U &= \begin{pmatrix} u \\ u' \\ u'' \\ u''' \\ \dots \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 & 0 & 0 \dots \\ a & b & 0 & 0 \dots \\ a & b & c & 0 \dots \\ a & b & c & d \dots \\ \dots & & & \dots \end{pmatrix} \\
\text{Tr } U &= \|a\| + \|b\| + \|c\| + \|d\| + \dots
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming whatever u, u', u'', \dots can be, trace can be unique combination of givens, regarding decomposition that basis can be drawn.

2.2.2 Fourier Transformation

Hyperplane in Fourier transformation makes unique chance in decomposition to arbitrary size of fixed points.

$$F(x) = a_1 \sin \theta_1 + a_2 \sin \theta_2 + a_3 \sin \theta_3 + \dots$$

Assuming function series that F_n is power n to given series of sin:

$$F_n(x) = a_1 \sin^n \theta_1 + a_2 \sin^n \theta_2 + a_3 \sin^n \theta_3 + \dots$$

Where power of sines can be driven from Cauchy-Schwarz inequality. More to say, with well-known equation of $\sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta = 1$, every power of n to $n + 1$ draws new hyperplane.

2.2.3 Lagrange Multiplier

Hyperplane in Lagrange multiplier is regarded as essential in compared to consisting its sum total, optimizing given dimensions with additional dimension.

$$h(a, b, c, d) \rightarrow f(a, b, c, \lambda g(e, f))$$

Upper occasion creates hyperplane $g(e, f)$ with variant λ . So to say, all the generalization can be possible in this λ, g occasion.

3 Cross Product Revisited

Then, availability of cross product in these three cases can be discussed.

$$a \times b = \|a\| \|b\| \sin \theta$$

The meaning of sine can be regarded as (sometimes vertical) new (hyperplane) dimension.

References

[김성기(2011)] 계승혁 김성기, 김도한. *해석개론(개정판 2판)*. September 2011.